

Instructional Supervision and Improved Teaching Performance for Public Primary Schools in Somalia

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Abstract

This paper discussed instructional supervision as a vital administrative tool for improving teachers' job performance in Somalia public primary schools. Instructional supervision is a series of actions intended to enhance the process of teaching and learning. The performance of teachers as highlighted in the paper is measured in terms of syllabus completion, lesson planning, and preparations, assessment and evaluation, and regular attendance. Supervision practices that can improve teaching performance include checking attendance in schools, inspecting the adequate interpretation of the curriculum and appropriate use of teaching methods, and evaluating the results of instructional activities. In Somalia. The paper also noted some major challenges faced in supervision and identified that there are inadequate supervisory personnel, lack of proper training,

lack of motivation, and poor leadership. The paper recommended the provision of in-service training programs to the supervisors in duties to enhance their capacity of practicing modern supervision. This can provide the supervisory skills needed and Proper staffing of the supervisory personnel by the educational administrators.

Keywords: *Curriculum, Instructional supervision, Primary schools, Supervision, Teachers' performance,*

Introduction

One of the operational roles of school administration that has historically been and is still very difficult to manage in primary schools is the supervisory duty. In consideration of this, Wabuko (2016) argued that over time, principals' teaching and administrative responsibilities have diminished, and supervisory duties have become more important. School leaders are responsible for adopting different strategies to influence teacher performance in the workplace. The origins of supervision can be found in the early American Educational System in the year 1642 according to Okumbe (2007). In Uganda, education supervision began in 1925 when the government began to exert control over education by creating a Directorate of Instruction Standards to guarantee excellent education in all educational institutions.

Instructional supervision is one of the two types of school supervision to improve learning. Instructional supervision is a series of actions intended to enhance the effectiveness in teaching and learning processes (Archibong, 2012). Therefore, the creation and execution of a work plan might be aided by instructional supervision. Lesson plans, participation in co-curricular activities, student discipline management, counseling and guidance, attendance at staff meetings, actual teaching, routine learner assessment, upkeep of records of work completed and learners' records, and time management are all considered to be teacher's performance (Ampofo et al., 2019).

In the 1970s, school principals and District inspectors were trained to observe teachers in the classrooms and to provide helpful comments, which marked the beginning of instructional supervision in Somalia. The Ministry of Education was in charge of monitoring all schools in various regions of the nation to improve their performance, and teacher supervision and feedback also became highly practical and detailed. Following the Somali state's collapse, many private schools appeared and developed their own methods for supervising teachers in the classroom (El-Shibiny, 1970).

The national school supervision report for Somalia was published in 2022 and included data from 1,742 primary and secondary schools in the states of Galmudug, Hirshabelle, Jubbaland, South-West, and the Banadir Regional Administration. According to the results of the supervisory exercise, primary schools without a secondary wing performed the worst, receiving an overall grade of 43%, while those with both primary and secondary sections received a score of 54%. The majority of important indicators, including the qualifications of primary school head teachers and deputies, the standard of school facilities, the availability of teaching and learning resources, the use of approved schemes of work, lesson plans, and lesson notes, among others, did not reflect well on primary schools. Therefore, this paper attempts to x-ray the role of instructional

supervision on the improvement of teaching performance by public primary school teachers' in Mogadishu.

The Concept of Instructional Supervision

The Latin term "Super video," which means "to oversee," is the origin of the English word "supervision." Instructional supervision is viewed from several perspectives by numerous educators. While some perceive it as a tool to provide rigorous leadership to teachers, others see it as a way to help teachers accomplish their class objectives. Archibong (2012) argues that the part of school administration known as instructional supervision is responsible for ensuring that the proper expectations of the educational system are met. The activities that are intended to enhance instruction at all levels of the educational enterprise are referred to as instructional supervision. Additionally, official organizational behavior that directly influences teacher behavior in order to promote student learning and further organizational objectives is known as instructional supervision.

Nwankwoala (2020) explained that "educational supervision also known as instructional supervision, is the process used by school principals, as well as supervisors from the Ministry of Education, to monitor, direct, control, and motivate classroom teachers during teaching and learning activities in order to help them meet the established instructional objectives and goals". From the above explanation, it is clear that instructional supervision is needed to enhance classroom instruction and the quality of the education system. The main goal of instructional supervision, therefore, is to help and support teachers as they change their behavior to deliver better lessons.

Furthermore, some scholars (Mohanty, 2008; Marecho, 2012; Panigrahi, 2012; Thakral, 2015) claim that instructional supervision still has the same general meaning as in Douglass and Bent's (1953) definition, which is to oversee, to superintend or to guide and to enhance the activities of others, with a view to their improvement (Lyonga, 2018). However, the current definitions of supervision place a strong focus on the growth of teachers' careers and the enhancement of the educational process. This means that instructional supervisors are like coaches giving instructions and support to the teachers instead of fault-finding.

Concept of Teacher Performance

In reality, three key elements—effort, competence, and direction—determine an employee's performance. This is why Nwankwoala (2020) opined that a teacher's performance is judged by a mix of how much effort was put into completing the work, how competent they were to do the task, and how well they grasped the goal of the activity. Upholding honesty, engaging in a maximal learning process, having a strong feeling of responsibility, setting clear goals, focusing on results, cooperating, working continually, and continuously improving are the fundamental principles of job performance.

On the other hand, Umaru (2018) believes that lesson planning, participation in school activities, student discipline management, counseling and guidance, staff meeting attendance,

actual teaching routine, learner assessment, upkeep of work-covered records, learners' records, and time management are all examples of how well teachers perform in their roles as educators (Umaru, 2018).

Indicators of Teacher Performance

According to Okia et al. (2021) The following is a breakdown of the teaching performance indicators, including syllabus covering, lesson planning and preparation, assessment and evaluation and regular attendance.

Syllabus coverage

Great efforts must be made to finish the syllabus in order to enhance the performance of both the teacher and the student. Sometimes insufficient experience among teachers and a lack of knowledge across all subject areas contribute to inadequate syllabi coverage. The teachers won't be able to work diligently toward finishing the syllabus without encouragement and acceptable gratifying behavior from the supervisors or teachers, and their performance is highlighted.

Lesson planning and preparation

Little can be done to ensure that teachers continue to advance professionally if one simply pays attention to what takes place in the classroom and ignores what occurs during the planning phase prior to the implementation of the lesson. The task of the teacher is made easier in terms of delivery when lesson plans are properly thought out and overseen since appropriate exercises, analogies, and demonstrations may be agreed upon to accommodate to the various cognitive skills of students. A well-prepared lesson plan, an approved scheme of work, and a severe lack of necessary supplies and equipment for efficient teaching and learning, are all clearly not being used

by teachers as intended, according to the Ministry of Education of Somalia's 2022 supervision report.

Assessment and evaluation

Teaching that ignores the evaluation and assessment of students is insufficient. This is due to the teacher's inability to assess how well the intended lesson objectives have been met. The two types of assessment are formative and summative. While summative aims at achieving final ratings that record each learner's performance relative to others, formative aims to aid learners by providing feedback on their performance that helps them develop and learn (Okia et al, 2021).

Regular attendance

Every school administrator and decision-maker should place a high priority on making investments in a school system that maintains qualified educators in the classroom. School administrators also argue that for such approaches to be effective, an environment where regular teacher attendance is the norm that must be created. In this environment, the school administration must track specific information about teacher attendance in order to raise teacher attendance.

The above indicators show that instructional supervisors should not only focus on what happens in the classroom but also before entering it. This means that how lessons are planned and prepared should also be checked during the supervision practice.

Challenges and Problems of Instructional Supervision in Somalia

Supervisors in Somalia still adhere to the inspection standards that were thought to be appropriate during the colonial era and the early post-colonial period of Somalia. Due to its lack of support for colleagues, this lowered instructional services and did not contribute to teachers'

career growth. Some of the main challenges facing instructional supervision in Somalia are as follows:

- **Insufficient number of supervisory personnel** - Some schools may go an entire term or session without having an instructional supervisor's visit. This is due to the fact that few supervisors are assigned to the public primary schools in Somalia.
- **Lack of proper training** - many school supervisors do not get appropriate training before and during the supervision practice. They also lack expertise since many young teachers are assigned to this supervision duty. Educational administrators in Somalia do not think supervisors should receive adequate training to provide supervisory services. The main requirements for hiring supervisors include having a first degree in education and having had some teaching experience.
 - **Lack of motivation for teachers and the supervisors** – It has been noted that poor performance of inspectors at our primary schools has been caused by a lack of motivation. Because some of the few available supervisors are owed salaries, they are not sufficiently motivated. Classroom teachers on the other hand are equally not being motivated to carry out their instructional responsibilities even with little or no supervision.
- **Poor leadership style** - Negative attitudes from supervisees to supervision pose significant challenges or limitations to school-based instruction supervision. The majority of supervisors are not exposed to participatory culture, so they continue to use outdated inspection methods.
- **Gap between the supervisor and supervisee** – many supervisors do not recognize the necessity of making themselves available to their clients for support. Supervisors do not

coach the supervisees during and after the supervision They only report what they have seen in the classroom but do not share this information with the teachers they supervise.

Conclusion

This paper examined instructional supervision as a veritable tool for improving teaching performance by public primary school teachers in Somalia. Various opinions and researches cited in this paper indicate that instructional supervision is a vital administrative strategy of improving teaching performance. Monitoring teachers' work plans, keeping tabs on teachers' attendance at school and in class, keeping tabs on teachers' preparation of instructional materials, supervising teachers on matters pertaining to curriculum interpretation, appropriate use of teaching methods, and evaluating the results of instructional activities are all aspects of instructional supervisory practices that aim to improve teaching performance. Instructional supervision is aimed at achieving the quality of teaching and learning and support for teachers to perform effectively on their duties. Undermining instructional supervision is setting a dangerous precipice for poor teaching performance and lowering standards in the educative process.

Recommendations

Based on the challenges and problems of instructional supervision in public primary schools in Somalia, the study recommended:

- Provision of in-service training programs to the supervisors to enhance their capacity to practice modern supervision. This can provide supervisory skills needed.
- Proper staffing of the supervisory personnel by the educational administrators.
- Supervisors should include their sub-ordinates and supervisees in the decision-making process to promote cooperation.
- The salary of the instructional supervisors should be increased to enhance their level of motivation. Benefits and allowances should also be allocated to the supervisors based on their performance.
- Creating platforms that enable supervisors to perform only supervisory services. This allows them to have adequate time to supervise and visit as many schools as possible.
- Supervision should not be a fault finding activity as it were, but should be more of a positive interaction between the teacher and the supervisor.
- The essence of instructional supervision is to support and guide the teacher positively, therefore supervisors should endeavour to share their observations politely with teachers.

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